

Bradford HDRC Policy Brief

Poverty and Schools. What Can We Do?

Target Audience: Schools and Local Authorities

Based on N8 Child of the North Report - An evidence-based plan for addressing poverty with and through schools

CotN_Poverty_Report_2.pdf

Key Evidence Based Messages

- **Poverty has substantial impacts on education.** In England, 60% of pupils receiving free school meals reach expected levels of reading in KS1, compared to 74% of the general pupil population.
- **There is a cumulative impact of poverty on health and education.** This includes psychological distress, self-assessed ill health, smoking, obesity, school absence and poor education achievement.
- **Geographic and demographic factors influence child poverty rates.** This requires place-based approaches as a response.
- **Educational settings offer outstanding opportunities to address poverty and food insecurity.** Efforts to address child poverty could be usefully organised around educational settings.
- **National level focus:**
 - Build Prioritise eradication of child poverty.
 - Develop a national strategy that uses education to tackle child poverty.
 - Level up in areas where education supports the most disadvantaged communities.
 - Frame as a public health problem.
- **Local level focus:**
 - Develop place based community approaches, based around schools and nurseries. Develop poverty strategies in schools.
 - Build on the approaches trialled in practice, highlighted in this briefing.

The Problem: 4 million children live in poverty in the UK. This has far reaching consequences for their rest of their lives and places huge pressure on public services

Mitigating inequality in early childhood (rather than a single focus on absolute poverty) would reduce the number of children experiencing multiple adversities by more than 80%.

"Huge numbers of us are now almost completely unable to support ourselves or our families. Nothing is affordable. Our children are hungry. Schools report 'short concentration' and 'unmanageable moods'. They have lost their childhood."

- "Changing Realities" participant.

58% of children in the North of England live in a local authority with above average levels of low-income families compared to 19% of rest of England

1.05 million children are living in poverty in the North Alone

46% of children from Black and minority ethnic groups live in poverty compared to 26% of white children.

Around one-third of the increase in infant mortality in the UK between 2014 and 2017 can be attributed to rising child poverty

What you can do at a local level

- **Adopt place-based approaches to addressing issues of poverty.** Focus on tailored approaches, based on insights provided by people with lived experiences
- **Implement poverty strategies in Schools** that address the barriers children living in poverty face. For example, school-based interventions such as Poverty Proofing© - an initiative that addresses the 'Cost of the School Day' (see below)
- **Emphasise Community-based interventions.** Work with and through schools to offer broad educational opportunities in an area of multiple deprivation.
- **Develop the kinds of programmes highlighted below.**

Approaches trialled in practice

Example	Approach	Impact
Poverty Proofing© the school day	Identifies the barriers children living in poverty face to engaging fully with school life and its opportunities and tries to ensure that 'no activity or planned activity in school should identify, exclude, treat differently or make assumptions about those with less financial resource'.	Minimised costs for schools and families, equal access to opportunities; greater poverty awareness and poverty sensitive policies and practices.
Department for Education Opportunity Areas	A placed-based programme targeted at areas of entrenched deprivation. Key features: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Place-based working in a holistic, bespoke approach that is tailored to each community's specific needs. • Targeted funding for designated areas and building on local knowledge to enable deployment of the expertise needed to enact change. • Established relationships and diverse partnerships with local stakeholders. 	Major impact in areas such as Bradford through providing much-needed investment into education (enabling bespoke place-based support). Other impacts included on quality of education - core factors that drove improvement included leadership and central funding from government.
North of Tyne Combined Authority's (NTCA) approach to building an inclusive space for CYP to thrive	Combines two programmes to tackle entrenched regional and local inequalities by directly supporting children, families and schools. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. An Education Improvement programme focussed on direct support for schools and their workforce, responding to local need and innovating to improve educational attainment. 2. A poverty prevention programme that builds social and economic resilience within areas, working with both schools and employers. 	Programme resulted in poverty interventions in over 100 schools; provision of welfare and benefits advice at the school gates in 45 schools, achieving over £1.2M in benefit gains for residents and a specific focus on support in the critical first 1001 days of a child's life.
Tackling poverty and disadvantage through a Multi-Academy Trust	Multi-academy trust developed a social justice and equality charter to frame and structure policy and support for disadvantaged pupils.	Ensured Trust took broader view of disadvantage than that suggested by the pupil premium policy and eligibility for free school meals (FSM). System leads were appointed with a specific responsibility for researching hyperlocal poverty and poverty-informed teacher educator programmes were developed. This included supporting teachers to understand trauma-informed approaches to classroom practice.